

DEVELOPMENT OF POSTER PRESENTATION SKILL AMONG B.ED. STUDENT TEACHERS

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Abstract:

'As an experimental learning activity that stimulates curiosity and interest, encourages exploration and integration of concepts and provides students with a novel way of demonstrating understanding' (Handron 1994, in Bracher, Cantrell & Wilkie 1998). A poster is an abstract. The mistake most frequently made is to put too much information on your poster. Your poster should be an eye-catcher, containing a brief message, understood at a glance. It is claimed that you have about three seconds to catch the audience's attention. To achieve this "three second hit" there are some aspects that you can take into account when you set out to design a poster. This brief didactic paper addresses the issues that help you create an attractive and effective poster.

Key Words: Development, Poster presentation, B.Ed. Student teachers

Introduction:

Posters are an excellent alternative medium for developing communication skills, helpful to involve students in the assessment process, encourage students to investigate a topic thoroughly, provide opportunities for peer learning, promote a positive attitude in students, exploring and confronting misconceptions. (Berry and Houston, 1995).

Concept mapping is a technique for representing knowledge in graphs, knowledge graphs network of concepts, network consists of nodes and links, nodes represent concepts and links, represent the relations between concepts. Concepts and links are labelled; links can be non-, unifier bi directional. Concepts and links may be categorized. They can be simply associative, specified, or divided in categories such as causal or temporal relations. Purpose of the concepts mapping are to generate ideas (brain storming, etc.), to design a complex structure (long texts, hypermedia large web sites, etc.), to communicate complex ideas, to aid learning by explicitly integrating new and old knowledge, to assess understanding or diagnose misunderstanding.

When researcher wants to present his research poster presentation is one of the best method for viewers and audience.

Steps in poster Design:

- ❖ What is the "overall message" you intend to present?
- ❖ Define your audience: who do you want to reach? How expert are they?
- ❖ What can you assume to be common knowledge?
- ❖ What should the audience remember?
- ❖ Gather content: before editing, write down all aspects of your message that you can think of – the essential issues, arguments, items of evidence, explanation, and conclusions.
- ❖ Create sections: classify the information that you have gathered.

Considering these elements of poster presentation, concept mapping and critical thinking researcher has decided to develop the poster presentation skill among B.Ed. student teacher.

Need and importance of study:

1. Poster presentation is the better way to present the research and difficult concepts with different ideas. So this research will help to students to present their ideas.
2. Concepts mapping and critical thinking are also higher level thinking, if we want to develop higher level thinking we have to conduct the activities.

3. Teacher educators and student teachers get the benefit that they can present their posters and concept maps, if they have developed this skill.

Statement of research problem:

Development of Poster Presentation Skill among B.Ed. Student Teachers

Objectives of research:

1. To know the problems of B.Ed. student teachers while preparing the posters.
2. To develop the poster presentation skill among B.Ed. student teachers.

Scope and limitations of research:

- This research has studied the poster presentation skill among B.Ed. student teachers of Geography Methodology.
- This research was restricted to Uma College of Education, Pandharpur student teachers of academic year 2017-18 only.

Research procedure:

Researcher has selected descriptive survey school survey method for this research. Sample for this research was 17 Geography Methodology students. Researcher first gives complete theoretical information regarding 'Best Poster Presentation'. Researcher has prepared poster evaluation scale for evaluation.

Analysis and interpretation of data:

This scale has 10 criterions for the evaluation of poster. Researcher has selected 17 posters and evaluated these posters with the help of evaluation scale.

Findings of the research:

1. Initially Student – teachers have problem that they could not decide the topic for poster presentation.
2. Student – teachers have used different skills, Designs and ideas for the preparation of posters.
3. Student – teachers have designed their posters effectively by considering standard norms of designing the posters.
4. Student- teachers have selected topics of their choice according to syllabus of geography methodology.
5. Student - teachers have selected different presentation techniques and types for poster presentation.
6. Every student- teacher have discussed with their colleagues and with teacher educator for preparation of poster.
7. Concepts mapping was used by every student teacher. They have also used different concepts designs and patterns for poster presentation.
8. Critical thinking, different ideas and problem solving skills were used in poster presentation by student - teachers.
9. Student- teachers have followed the instructions of teacher educator for the preparation of poster.
10. All the student- teachers have responded that they have satisfaction in the skill for poster presentation.

Educational Implications:

Student teachers are enriched their poster presentation skill and also they have got the experience of presentation of their different ideas with the help of posters. In this process they undergone through higher level thinking.

References:

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